

Entomopathogenic Fungi – An ecological alternative to chemical pesticides

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Introduction

Insects are susceptible to a variety of diseases caused by viruses, bacteria, fungi, protozoans, rickettsia, mycoplasma and nematodes. Among them, fungal pathogens have certain advantages over other insect pathogens like bacteria and viruses and gaining importance in crop pest control in recent years. Entomopathogenic fungi are a major component of integrated pest management techniques as a biological control agent against the insect pests and other arthropods in horticulture, forestry and agriculture and are found in the divisions of Zygomycota, Ascomycota, Deuteromycota, Chytridiomycota and Oomycota. They comprise of wide range of morphologically, phylogenetically and ecologically diverse fungal species. As a group of parasites, the entomopathogenic fungi infect a wide range of insect hosts, from aquatic larvae to adult insects from high canopies in tropical forests or even deserts. Their hosts are spread among 20 of the 31 orders of insects, in all developmental stages: eggs, larvae, pupae, nymphs, and adults.

Advantages of Entomofaunal pathogens over other groups of microbial agents:

- Mass production is much simpler, easier and cheaper
- Unlike bacteria or viruses do not require ingestion
- Play an important role in natural pest control through epizootics
- No report of Resistance development for fungal pathogens
- Ideally suited component in Integrated Pest Management (IPM)

Entomopathogenic fungi for pest suppression

More than 750 species of fungi, mostly Deuteromycetes and Entomophthorales from about 100 genera are pathogenic to insects, and many of them offer great potential for pest management. Species that have been most intensively investigated for mycoinsecticides in crop pest control include *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Lecanicillium lecanii* (= *Verticillium lecanii*), *Hirsutella thompsonii*, *Nomuraea rileyi*, *Isaria fumosoroseus* (= *Paecilomyces fumosoroseus*), *Isaria farinosa* (= *Paecilomyces farinosus*) etc (Table-1). The first two species have been used on large scale for the control of several crop pests over a number of years, while others have been attempted in recent times.

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The fungal diseases of insects are commonly referred to as mycosis. Fungi infect insects of almost all orders, most common in Hemiptera, Diptera, Coleoptera, Lepidoptera, Orthoptera and Hymenoptera. In some insect orders, nymphal or larval stages are more often infected than the adult stages, in others the reverse may be the case. Fungi rarely infect the pupal and egg stages. Some fungi have restricted host ranges, e.g., *Aschersonia aleyrodis* infects only whiteflies and scales, *Zoophthora aphidis* infects only aphids from one genus, while others like *B.bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* infect more than 700 species in several insect orders and they have several pathotypes which have a high degree of host specificity.

Table-1: Common Entomogenous Fungi and their Hosts.

Entomogenous fungus	Host
Zygomycotina	
<i>Entomophthora muscae</i>	Dipteran insects
<i>E. thripidium</i>	Thrips
<i>Entomophaga aulicae</i>	Lepidopteran insects
<i>E. grylli</i>	Orthopteran insects
<i>Erynia neoaphidis</i>	Aphids
<i>Massospora cicadina</i>	Cicada
<i>Neozygites fresenii</i>	Aphids
<i>Zoophthora radicans</i>	Certain Hemiptera and Lepidoptera

<i>Conidiobolus obscurus</i>	Aphids
Deuteromycotina	
<i>Aschersonia aleyrodis</i>	Whiteflies, Scales
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	Wide host range
<i>B.brongniartii</i>	Cockchafers and sugarcane borer
<i>Hirsutella thompsonii</i>	Spider mite, citrus red mite, coconut eriophyid mite
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	Wide host range
<i>M. flavoviride</i>	Orthopteran insects
<i>Nomuraea rileyi</i>	Lepidoptera
<i>Isaria farinose</i>	Coleoptera, Lepidoptera
<i>I. fumosoroseus</i>	Wide host range
<i>Lecanicillium lecanii</i>	Wide host range (Aphids, Whiteflies, Scales)

Fungal pathogenesis on insects: Most of the EPF infect the host through the cuticle. The process of pathogenesis begins with adhesion of fungal spore on cuticle followed by germination, penetration and development of fungus inside the host leading to the death of the host. Fungi usually cause insect mortality by nutritional deficiency, destruction of tissues and releasing of toxins. After the penetration of germinating hyphae in the haemocoel, the fungus produces hyphal bodies, hyphal strands and protoplasts that fill the haemocoel completely. Several mycotoxins

are produced by these fungi during pathogenesis and these act-like poisons for the insects (Table-2). After the death of the insects the fungus breaks open the integuments and form aerial mycelia and sporulation on the cadavers.

Symptoms of Fungal Infections on Insects

- Loose appetite, coordination, less active
- Cadavers - hard
- Cadavers - fungal growth and sporulation
- Whitish/Creamish fungal growth *B. bassiana*, *L. lecanii*
- Greenish sporulation- *M. anisopliae*, *N. rileyi*

Environmental conditions particularly humidity and temperature play an important role in the infection and sporulation of entomopathogenic fungi. Very high humidity (> 90% RH) and an optimum temperature of 25° C is required for spore germination and epizootics.

References:

Bamisile, B. S., Akutse, K. S., Siddiqui, J. A. and Xu, Y., 2021. Model application of entomopathogenic fungi as alternatives to chemical pesticides: Prospects, challenges, and insights for next-generation sustainable agriculture. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 12.

Faria, M. R. and S. P. Wraight, 2007. Mycoinsecticides and mycoacaricides: A comprehensive list with worldwide coverage and international classification of formulation types. *Biological Control*, 43: 237-256

Rai, D., Updhyay, V., Mehra, P., Rana, M. and Pandey, A.K., 2014. Potential of entomopathogenic fungi as biopesticides. *Indian Journal of Science Research and Technology*, 2(5): 7-13.

<https://vikaspedia.in/agriculture/crop-production/integrated-pest-managment/role-of-entomopathogenic-fungi-in-insect-pest-management>.

Table 2 : Toxins Produced by Entomopathogenic Fungi

Sl. No.	Fungus	Toxin produced
1	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	Beauvericin, Beauverolides, Bassinolide
2	<i>B. brongniartii</i>	Isarolides A, B, C, D
3	<i>Metarhizium</i>	Destruxins A, B, C, D, E, F
4	<i>Isaria</i>	Isarin
5	<i>Lecanicillum lecanii</i>	Similar to Bassinolide
6	<i>Cordyceps miliaris</i>	Cordycepin

Table 3: Biological Control of pests using entomopathogenic fungi

Fungus	Pest & Crop	Field efficacy	Reference
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	Rice Hispa (<i>Diuraphis armigera</i>)	A spray of <i>B. bassiana</i> spore suspension 10 million spores/ml	Hazarika and Puzari (1997)
	Coffee berry borer (<i>Hypothenemus hampei</i>)	A spray of <i>B. bassiana</i> spore suspension (1×10^7 spores/ml) containing 0.1% sunflower oil and 0.1% wetting agent during monsoon reduced 50-60% berry borer incidence in Coorg, Karnataka	Anon. (2001)
	Tea looper caterpillar (<i>Buzura suppressaria</i>)	A spray of <i>B. bassiana</i> spore suspension (2.5 g/l), reduced 88% reduction in West Bengal	Ghatak and Reza (2007)
	Sunflower <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	A spray of oil suspension of <i>B. bassiana</i> (200mg/l) in Andhra Pradesh	Devi and Hari (2009)
	Green gram White grubs	Soil application @ 5×10^{13} conidia/ha effective control achieved in Assam	Bhattacharyya <i>et al.</i> (2008)
<i>Beauveria Brongniarti</i>	Sugarcane white grubs <i>Holotrichia serrata</i>	Soil application @ 1kg /acre. Highest yield recorded	Chelvi <i>et al.</i> (2010)
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	Coconut Rhinoceros beetle (<i>Oryctes rhinoceros</i>)	Spraying of Spores in its breeding sites @ 5×10^{11} spores/m ³ to the compost pits and manure heaps	Anon. (2000)
	Sugarcane White grub	<i>M. anisopliae</i> at 1×10^{13} /ha gave a yield of 91.18 q/ha as compared with chlorpyrifos (93.29 q/ha) in Karnataka.	Rachappa <i>et al.</i> (2004)
	Pigeon Pod borer <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	<i>M. anisopliae</i> conidia in an oil formulation was effective in reducing 66.74% <i>H. armigera</i> as compared to 62.58% with endosulfan in Maharashtra.	Nahar <i>et al.</i> (2004)
	Potato White grubs (<i>Brahmina</i>)	Soil application @ 5×10^{13} conidia/ha along with chlorpyrifos 20 EC at 200 g a.i./ha resulted in the highest tuber yield (155 q/ha) in HP.	Bhagat <i>et al.</i> (2003)
	Soyabean white grubs <i>Holotrichia longipennis</i>	Soil application formulation applied @ 5×10^{13} conidia/ha, 61.50% reduction in grub population	Pandey (2010)
<i>Lecanicilliumlecanii</i>	Coffee green scale (<i>Coccus viride</i>)	Spraying spores @ 16×10^6 spores/ml along with Tween-80 twice at 2 weeks interval caused 97.6% mortality of the pest.	Jayaraj (1989)
	Citrus green scale (<i>Coccus viride</i>)	Spraying of spore (2×10^6 spores/ml) along with 0.005% quinalphos and 0.05% Teepol was found highly effective in killing 95.58% and 97.55% scales in coffee and citrus respectively	Singh (1995)
	Indian mustard and Rapeseed-Mustard aphid <i>Lipaphis erysimi</i>	Spray @ (10^6 spores/ml). There was a significant reduction in aphid infestation at 10 DAS.	Rana <i>et al.</i> (2002)
<i>Nomuraea rileyi</i>	Castor <i>Spodoptera litura</i> in AP	Spraying of spore (10×10^{10} spores/ml) along with 0.02% Tween-80.	Vimala Devi and Prasad (1997)
	Soybean <i>Spodoptera litura Helicoverpa armigera Thysonoplusia orichalcea</i>	<i>N. rileyi</i> spores spraying @ 2×10^8 /ml twice at 10 days intervals during Kharif in North Karnataka. Cheaper than insecticidal treatment and cost effective.	Lingappa <i>et al.</i> (2002)

